

PREREVIEW

OPEN GRANT REVIEWERS

REVIEWER GUIDE

WHAT IS IT AND WHO IS IT FOR?

This Grant Reviewer Guide is a comprehensive, step-by-step framework designed to help anyone who is going through the process of reviewing a grant application proposal, whether as directly invited to participate as an external reviewer, or selected through a call for reviewers.

We believe this guide can be helpful to early-career researchers, scholars, and professionals that were invited to participate to grant review for the first time and want to learn more, and even to experienced reviewers looking to gain an additional detailed understanding and new perspective on how to grant review.

This Grant Reviewer Guide is part of a toolkit developed in the context of the **Open & Equitable Model Funding Program**, a cohort-based project determined to foster open research practices to create a more transparent, equitable, and collaborative research ecosystem. The content of the guide is largely adapted from the **Open Reviewers Reviewer Guide** (Foster et al., 2021)—a framework for reviewers going through the process of writing a manuscript review. It contains references to resources and materials openly available, such as the **PLOS Peer Review Center's** adapted in the context of the grant review process. Content adapted from the **PLOS Peer Review Center** will be italicized. From here on in, we will refer to “**you**”, as the reviewer and reader of this guide.

HOW SHOULD YOU USE IT?

The content of this guide is organized into three sections.

Section 1 (**To Review or Not to Review**) provides you with some example grant review scenarios and prompts you to reflect on the decision of accepting or declining to review a grant application proposal. It also includes a list of what we think are the top most important traits of a “good” reviewer (**What Makes a Good Grant Reviewer**).

Section 2 (**Writing a Review: Step-by-Step**) is where we break down the review process into 6 actionable steps. When going through STEPS 1-4, we recommend you focus on reading, observing, then evaluating the manuscript following the suggested actions, trying not to focus too much on the actual writing of the review—however you can use the next section to take notes as you move through the steps. Piecing together the final review will be the main action in STEP 5. STEP 6 is another opportunity to reflect on your review and make adjustments prior to sharing it with the program officers, chair, scientific review officers, or anyone involved in the application review process.

Section 3 (**Writing a Review: Print-Out**) is a walk-through of the 6 steps, with guiding questions we invite you to reflect on, and space to add notes as you move through the steps. If you are the type of reviewer who prefers paper and pen to jot down ideas and organize them into a coherent piece, we recommend that you print out the section so that you can have it side-by-side with the grant proposal to assess as you read through it. Alternatively, you can make a copy of an editable version of this section made available in a shared **Open Grant Reviewers Google Drive document**.

This Reviewer Guide will guide you through the 6 steps of composing a manuscript review.

1 Adapted from the **PLOS Peer Review Center's** “Useful ideas on what to consider before agreeing to review a manuscript for a journal.”

TO REVIEW OR
**NOT TO
REVIEW**

TO REVIEW OR **NOT TO REVIEW**

This guide applies to any situation that involves you, a researcher, professional, or activist called to act as “the expert” to provide feedback to a grant application proposal in your field of study.

Scenario 1: You have been invited by a funding agency to **review a grant application proposal** for the development of a project in your field.

Some questions you can ask yourself before agreeing to review a grant proposal include:

1. Am I the right person to review this grant proposal?

You should only review a manuscript if it matches your area of expertise. Even if the topic sounds fascinating, don't agree to review it if you do not have the expertise.

If you are not sure you have the right expertise, or if you think you could provide an expert evaluation of one aspect of the manuscript but not all of it, get in touch with the journal to see what they need. No matter what, it is important that you feel comfortable offering your opinion.

Note: The definition of “expertise” is rather subjective, and often more tied with prestige and seniority in a given field rather than with any actual experience in reviewing other people’s work constructively. Furthermore, if you are an individual from an historically marginalized group or an early-career professional, you may be less confident in calling yourself an expert. Finally, rarely a reviewer is an expert in every aspect of someone else’s work. We invite you to consider these potential internalized and possibly unconscious biases when deciding if you are the right person for the job. If you are in doubt contact the program staff and let them know about your concerns. But be aware that program officers and chairs themselves are not immune to bias.

The definition of expertise is rather subjective, and often more tied with prestige and seniority in a given research field rather than with any actual experience in reviewing other people’s work constructively.

2. Do I have time to do the review by the funding program's deadline?

Don't overcommit: make sure you have enough time to provide a thorough review. If you want to review but think you might need extra time to get it done, let the program officers or staff know as soon as possible so that they can decide if an extension is feasible.

3. Can I provide an objective review?

Before you respond to the invitation and if available, check the applicants' list in case you have past or present collaborations with any of them, or any other potentially competing interests. You should decline the invitation if an outside observer might reasonably feel that your review was negatively or positively biased by a competing interest.

If you're not sure if you have a competing interest, or think you have one but it won't compromise your objectivity, get in touch with the program officers or staff. The program might want you to review it anyway, depending on the situation

Additionally, we recommend you become aware of other common biases and assumptions that may arise when reviewing. The truth is that **being completely objective is virtually impossible**. In STEPS 1 and 6 of our **Writing a Review: Step-by-Step** section, we will invite you to think deeply about the ways assumptions or biases may be affecting your assessment of the manuscripts you choose to review.

Be aware of common biases and assumptions that arise when reviewing.

It is okay to decline the invitation.

You do not have to say yes to everything! If you have doubts about your ability to do the review or your availability to review on time, it is much better to say no upfront than to step down later on. Whether you accept or decline the assignment, try to respond to the invitation as quickly as you can. It's not fair to the applicants and program staff to keep them waiting.

Note: If you decide to decline, consider providing the program officers or staff with the names of other suitable reviewers. This is something you may think about even if you do have time and have no competing interests. For example, you may know someone who had fewer opportunities than you to be a reviewer and who may provide a different perspective to the review that you may not be able to provide given your background and experience.

WHAT MAKES A "GOOD" GRANT REVIEWER?

The number one attribute a funding program looks for in a reviewer is an appropriate level of expertise within the fields of the program itself. Other traits that we believe are equally important to qualify you as a "good" grant reviewer are the following:

- **Respectful.** A good grant reviewer values respect above all and knows not to make their peers feel diminished or personally attacked by disrespectful comments.
- **Constructive.** A good grant reviewer ensures that their feedback is constructive and actionable so that applicants can easily respond to the feedback and possibly integrate the suggestions into the final project.
- **Honest.** A good grant reviewer knows that constructive does not mean they need to lie or only bring up positive comments. It means they need to write their suggestions in a way that is not insulting to the applicants and that can lead to their easy integration into the proposal. Constructive comments followed by examples and suggestions on how to improve the issue generate more actionable feedback.
- **Clear.** A good grant reviewer strives to present suggestions in clear language, avoiding jargon and, when possible, providing examples and links to additional information that can help the applicants make an informed decision on whether or not to integrate such suggestions.
- **Humble.** A good grant reviewer is willing to be wrong and corrects themselves along the way.
- **Aware.** A good grant reviewer is self-reflective and takes time to assess their biases and examines how they think and operate in the world.

WRITING A GRANT APPLICATION
REVIEW:
STEP-BY-STEP

WRITING A REVIEW: **STEP-BY-STEP**

This is all great, but in practice, you may be wondering, *how do I go about writing a grant application review?*

Writing a grant application review, especially for the first few times, can feel like a daunting task. But almost everything gets easier when it is broken down into smaller, manageable steps.

Below is our attempt to break down the process of writing a review into **6 STEPS**:

STEP 1: CHECK YOUR **BIASES AND ASSUMPTIONS**

Before beginning to read and assess the grant proposal you are set to review, we recommend reading through the **Grant Review Bias Reflection Guide** to help you identify and mitigate biases or assumptions that may arise. This exercise is not intended to judge your approach to reviewing or tell you if you have or do not have biases. It is an opportunity for you to take a moment to reflect and set your mind on the main goal of reviewing: *Provide objective and constructive feedback to the applicants to improve the quality of the grant proposal and the projects themselves.*

ACTION: Read through the **Bias Reflection Guide** and *observe* your thoughts without judgment. Consider using the space allocated to this step in the **Writing a Grant Review: Print-Out** to *take notes* so that you can revisit these thoughts in STEP 6.

STEP 2: GAIN A **CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING**

Before diving into the details of your review, it is good practice to read the whole grant proposal at once to gain an *overall understanding* of what the hypotheses or main questions, general and specific objectives, and proposed outputs of the proposed project are. Doing this will help you write what is usually the first paragraph of a review, a summary of the project and your overall impression. Note that you will be guided into the writing of the summary paragraph in STEP 5, but notes from this step can help you piece that out later.

ACTION: Read through the manuscript once with your “big picture” hat on, making sure you focus on *understanding* rather than evaluating. Consider using the space allocated to this step in the **Writing a Grant Review: Print-Out** section to answer some guiding questions.

Note: Evaluation thoughts will inevitably pop up during this time, but understanding before evaluating can help us avoid bias.

Next are some questions² you may find useful to keep in mind during this first read-through (these are repeated in the **Writing a Grant Review: Print-Out** section to guide you through this step):

- **What is the project about?** *What is the scope and main objective of the project?*
- **What is the approach?** *What are the applicants addressing to achieve the project goals?*
- **What is the context?** *How does the project relate to funding program objectives and goals?*
- **What are the proposed outcomes?** *What are the applicants' proposed outcomes and how are they related to the main objectives of the project and the program itself?*

A useful approach to help you gain a first conceptual understanding of the project is to read the proposal out of order. A detailed example of this approach is:

- Read the **abstract and scope of the project** to get a sense of the overall context and approach (if the abstract and introduction do not do a good job summarizing the findings, you might need to read further to get this information).
- Identify the main and specific objectives of the proposal.
- Look at the **figures and tables** carefully in conjunction with the results.
- Read the **conclusions**.
- Then read the **whole thing** from beginning to end.

²Adapted from the **PLOS Peer Review Center's** list of questions you may find useful to keep in mind during a first read.

STEP 3: EVALUATE, **APPRECIATE, RAISE CONCERNS**

Now that you have checked your biases and assumptions and gained a conceptual understanding of the grant application proposal, it is time to evaluate the work in more depth. The outcome of this step is a list of major and minor issues that, together with the constructive, clear, and actionable feedback (STEP 4), will make up the bulk of your final review (STEP 5).

ACTION: *Re-read* the proposal and *identify* issues you may have with the project. You may choose to simply *highlight* these in the proposal itself and then list and categorize them as major or minor issues. Consider using the space allocated to this step in the **Writing a Grant Review: Print-Out** section to answer some guiding questions.

Major issues should consist of the essential points the authors need to address before the manuscript can proceed. They are issues that if left unaddressed could compromise the interpretation of the study.

Major issues include:

- *The project proposal is out of the scope of the funding program's objectives and goals*
- *The proposed outcomes and deliverables are not related or are not relevant to the main objective of the proposal*
- *The proposed activities are not related or are not coherent with the general and specific objectives of the project*
- *Implementation time is not related to the activities or is not feasible for the project*

Minor issues are still important but typically will not affect the overall conclusions of the proposal.

Minor issues include:

- *Missing references (but depending on what is missing, this could also be a major issue)*
- *Technical clarifications (e.g., the applicants should clarify how a reagent works)*
- *Typos, spelling, grammar, and phrasing issues*

About evaluating references

As stated above, missing references is usually a minor issue, but it can be a major issue if you think the references missing are key to the interpretation and implementation of the proposal, or if you think several references have been made out of context.

A tool you may find useful to evaluate references are **Scite.ai** (Nicholson *et al.*, 2021), it will help you how the studies cited in the manuscript were cited by others and whether those citations offered supporting or contrasting evidence of the cited claims.

About typos and grammatical errors

While it may be tempting to focus on grammatical errors, sentence structure, and choice of words, try to make general language-related suggestions only if you think they may help with the understanding of the concept presented. This is particularly important to keep in mind if you are reviewing a grant proposal authored by applicants whose English is not their first language, as interpreting language mistakes as a lack of overall quality constitutes a common bias among reviewers.

About plagiarism

If you are reviewing for a funding organization and you have reasons to believe the applicants might have plagiarized the proposed research, contact the funding organization immediately. If there are confidential comments to the program officer section of the reviewer report/rubric add your concerns there.

Grant applications are typically assessed in terms of originality, relevance, soundness, and feasibility (Hug & Aeschbach, 2020).

Interpreting language mistakes as lack of overall quality constitutes a common bias among reviewers.

STEP 4: MAKE YOUR FEEDBACK **CLEAR, CONSTRUCTIVE, AND ACTIONABLE**

Now that you have read through the grant proposal in depth and identified major and minor issues of the application, it is time to begin thinking about how you will want to present those issues and how to suggest revisions in your review. Your feedback should be clear, constructive, and actionable. That way the applicants will not only be more likely to understand your feedback and integrate it efficiently into their work for future submissions, but will also appreciate it without feeling defensive or personally attacked.

This is arguably the most important and time-consuming step of the review process. As a reviewer, you play an important role in the decision-making process of selecting the projects to be funded, which means you have power in the life and scope of the program, the advances of the research in certain fields, and to foster equity in the grantmaking process.

ACTION: Read through your list of major and minor issues and identify ways to suggest improvements that are clear, constructive, and actionable. Consider using the space allocated to this step in the **Writing a Grant Review: Print-Out** section.

Here is an example.

Let's say you disagree with the use of a specific software solution for a given proposal. This would fall into the category of weaknesses of the project, possibly a major issue the applicants need to address or the expected results will be compromised. How would you go about writing up this negative feedback in your review?

Unclear, disruptive, an unactionable feedback:

"The applicants have no idea of what they are doing and should read and study more on software and hardware compatibility."

compared to,

Clear, constructive, actionable feedback:

"The proposal fails to address how the selected software solution [software X] will interact with the actual infrastructure and the relational databases to collect, preserve and publicly disseminate the datasets generated over the course of the project. The selected solution [software X] is not fully compatible with the described infrastructure and the most common object-oriented programming languages, like Java, for the implementation of relational databases and services, presented in the deliverables of the project. This requires knowledge of implementation on Ruby on rails, which is not listed in the expertise of the applicants. I suggest the use of [software Y], which is fully compatible with the actual infrastructure and build to work with Java. If the choice of [software X] is motivated by a particular strategy or other non-obvious purposes, it is recommended to explicitly mention that in the corresponding section justifying the choice accordingly."

In this last example language, we present our *interpretation of the issue* (remember it may be that we are misinterpreting something so it is good practice to phrase your opinion accordingly), followed by the *reason* we think it is an issue, followed by our *recommendation(s)* on how to go about addressing it. Also, note that oftentimes it is helpful to avoid referring to the applicants directly and keep the focus on the choice or the research, as *depersonalizing* your feedback can make the applicants feel respected and less defensive.

Note: This example shows that constructive feedback does *not* equal positive feedback. Your feedback can be honest and respectful at the same time.

About positive feedback

Even though thus far we asked you to focus on the issues, highlighting positive feedback, things you thought were done well in the grant proposal, is also a key aspect of a good review as it reinforces good practices we wish the applicants will continue adopting. Examples of positive feedback can include spotlighting novel contributions to the field, mentioning points of inspiration for your own future research, and emphasizing aspects of the work that fascinated you.

Importantly, data shows that overly-harsh or unprofessional peer reviews disproportionately harm underrepresented researchers (Silbiger NJ et al., 2019). Therefore, remember to strike a good balance between positive and negative feedback, keeping it all clear, constructive, and actionable.

Remember to strike a good balance between positive and negative feedback, keeping it all clear, constructive, and actionable.

About suggesting additional experiments and/or analyses

If your suggestion on how to address one or more of the major issues is for the applicants to perform additional activities or deliverables for the implementation of the grant proposal, it is important to stop and think if what you are suggesting is:

- Essential to supporting the success and feasibility of the project
- Feasible for this research group
- Within the scope of the funding program goals and terms of reference

It can be tempting to suggest changes or additional activities and deliverables that may be interesting and further expand upon the outputs in the grant proposal but are not essential for the success of the project. It is okay to share this type of information in your review; however, it is important to be clear about whether the recommended additions are essential to support the success of the project.

Let's say, for example, you are reviewing an application in which all experiments to develop for the project, are in vitro experiments, and what you are suggesting as an additional experiment requires an in vivo setup with which the laboratory is not equipped. As a general practice, you should not request that experiment as a condition for the application to be accepted. To conduct this additional activity the applicant would not only likely need several more time but also resources they may not currently have considered for the project. You can suggest that experiment as a follow-up project for the applicants to undertake themselves or in a next iteration of the grant opportunity. You may also suggest that the activities be reworded to better align with the existing scope and direction of the proposal.

However, if you believe that the actual scope and outcomes of the proposal as they currently stand would depend on the addition of these activities, the project proposal may not be quite ready for granting.

Consider carefully if the additional experiments or analyses you are suggesting are essential, feasible, and within the scope of the current study.

STEP 5: PUT IT ALL TOGETHER INTO A COHERENT NARRATIVE

It is now time to combine all that you have done up to this point into a coherent narrative that will make up your final review. Even though probably you will receive a review report for the assessment, it is useful to have a format in mind to help guide the writing. Here, we will use an adaptation of the review format proposed in the **PLOS Peer Review Center** as we find it easy to follow and comprehensive of the most important components of a review.

In addition to the information below, we also recommend you refer to the **Writing a Review: Print-Out** section which contains questions and prompts to guide you through the process of crafting your final review.

Schematic representation of a typical review format modified from *PLOS Peer Review Template: A quick guide for new peer reviewers*.

This review format includes three main sections. Let's take a look at each one of them.

1. Summary of the research and overall impression

Beginning your review with a summary paragraph helps the reader gain an overview of your perspective on the proposal and primes them for what comes next in the review. The reader, being the applicants, the funding program officers and staff, the Chairs and Scientific Review Officers, and/or anyone involved in the application review process reading your review.

ACTION: Write a short summary paragraph to contextualize the work and prime the reader to the rest of the review. The summary paragraph may include the following components:

- A sentence or two summarizing the **grant proposal's main objective and approach**;
- A brief overview of the project's **main strengths and weaknesses**;
- Your perspective on where the project sits in the **context of the funding program goals**;
- Your perspective on how the proposed project may **push the field forward or lead to future work**;
- If the funding program does not provide any other way for reviewers to express it, a **recommendation for the course of action**.

2. Evidence and Examples

This is the core of your review, the section where you present the issues or concerns you identified in the proposal and back it up with evidence and examples to best explain why you think those are issues and suggest how to address them as clearly, constructively, and actionably as possible. If you took notes during STEPS 3 and 4, this is the time to use them.

For this section, the **PLoS Peer Review Center** offers the following advice:

It's helpful to divide this section into two parts: one for major issues and one for minor issues. Within each section, you can talk about the biggest issues first or go systematically activity-by-activity or expected results per stage. Number each item so that your points are easy to follow (this will also make it easier for the authors to respond to each point). Refer to specific lines, pages, or sections so the applicants (and program officers and staff) know exactly what you're talking about.

3. Other points

If you made it here, congratulations! You are most of the way done! This last section is not strictly necessary, but it can provide a nice way to conclude your review and communicate any relevant information to the reader.

If applicable, add confidential comments for the program officers and staff. Raise any concerns about the proposal that they may need to consider further, such as concerns about ethics. Do not use this section for your overall critique. Also mention whether you might be available to look at a revised version in another round of review.

Other things you may consider adding in this space are information about potential Competing Interests (unless there is a separate, dedicated field in the review submission form), your expertise, and any aspects of the application proposal you did not feel confident about making suggestions because they lay outside of that expertise. You may even consider adding a sentence about something you learned by reading and reviewing this proposal and will now consider adopting into your own research practice.

About confidential comments to the editor

Some funding programs may provide a space for reviewers to enter confidential comments about the application proposals. Use this space to mention concerns about the submission that you'd want the program officers or staff to consider before sharing your feedback with the applicants, such as concerns about ethical guidelines or language quality. Any serious issues should be raised directly and immediately with the funding program's relevant staff as well.

Do not use this space to critique the manuscript, since comments entered here will not be passed along to the applicant. *If you're not sure what should go in the confidential comments, read the reviewer instructions or check with the program officer or staff first before submitting your review. If you are reviewing for a funding program that does not offer a space for confidential comments, consider writing to the program officer directly with your concerns*

About formatting: no one format fits it all

The review format proposed above is just one example. Reviews can be formatted in a variety of ways according to the funding program's guidelines and style if they are provided.

After some experience, you will see that some fellow reviewers chose to separate major and minor issues into separate sections, some reviewers write in full paragraphs, and others separate each point using a numbered list. If there are no program requirements on the structure, the decision is really up to you. If you only have a few things to convey, writing full paragraphs may work well to communicate your thoughts. If you have a lot of feedback, separating your points by numeric lists or by sections may be the best approach

 STEP 6: CHECK YOUR REVIEW AND SHARE IT

Congratulations on making it thus far! You should now have a fully written review that is ready for the final check before it is shared with others.

ACTION: *Read* through your review all at once to make sure your language is clear, your feedback is constructive and actionable, and correct any typos. Finally, we recommend that you revisit your notes from STEP 1 and the **Bias Reflection Guide** to make sure your review is as objective and unbiased as it can be.

Once you have your final review, it is time to share it with others. Follow the funding program guidelines or instructions on where and how to submit your review.

WRITING A GRANT REVIEW
PRINT-OUT

WRITING A REVIEW: **PRINT-OUT**

This section of the guide contains prompts and questions to lead you through the steps that were presented in the **Writing a Grant Application Review: Step-by-Step** section. Depending on your work style, you may decide to print this section and use the space provided under each question to scribble your notes as you move through the steps

STEP 1: ASSESS YOUR **PERSONAL BELIEFS**

ACTION: *Read* through the **Bias Reflection Guide** and *observe* your thoughts without judgment. Use the space below to take notes as you go about this process.

STEP 2: GAIN A **CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING**

ACTION: *Read* through the grant application proposal, once with your “big picture” hat on, making sure you focus on “understanding” rather than “evaluating”. Answering the questions below, which are adapted from the PLOS Peer Review Center³, may help you gain a conceptual understanding of the grant application proposal and help you craft the summary paragraph of your final review (STEP 5).

³ <https://plos.org/resource/how-to-read-a-manuscript-as-a-peer-reviewer>

What is the project about? What are the scope and main objective of the project?

What is the approach? What are the applicants addressing to achieve the project goals?

What is the context? How does the project relate to the funding program objectives and goals?

What are the proposed outcomes? What are the applicants' proposed outcomes and how are they related to the main objectives of the project and the program itself?

What did you find particularly/specifically interesting about the proposal?

 STEP 3: EVALUATE, APPRECIATE, RAISE CONCERNS

ACTION: *Re-read* the proposal and *identify* issues you may have with the project. The questions below are meant to help you guide through evaluating and raising concerns in each section of the grant proposal (e.g., Title, Summary or Abstract, Introduction, Problem or Need Statement, Objectives, Methodologies, Evaluation, Budget⁴).

You may find it easier to first identify the issues in each section and then categorize them as major and minor using any notation you wish—e.g., “M” for major issues and “m” for minor issues.

The following are only suggestions and examples of how a grant application could be composed. It may vary depending on the funding program’s goals and requirements.

Title

The *Title* should convey in one sentence key information about what the project is about, the project design, and important keywords so that interested readers can more easily find the work. The *Title* should *not* sensationalize or overreach the project proposal.

Does the Title appropriately reflect the content of the manuscript?

Summary or Abstract

The *Abstract* is a summary of the whole project proposal and should contain information about who is making the application, the need or problem being addressed, the objectives, methods, and costs. It should not sensationalize the proposal or speculate about how the project may lead to future work.

Does the abstract clearly state the scope of the project proposal?

Does the abstract clearly state the approach and the relation with the funding program’s objectives and goals?

Are the expected results and outcomes of the project presented?

⁴ Adapted from Colgate University. (n.d.). Basic Elements of a Grant Proposal. Colgate University. <https://www.colgate.edu/about/campus-services-and-resources/basic-elements-grant-proposal>

Note: Not all funding programs use the same name convention for grant application review formats.

Introduction

The *Introduction* should put the qualifications to carry out the project being proposed. It should contain information about why the proposed project matters and how it fits into the broader scheme of the funding program. Below are some questions adapted from the PLOS Peer Review Center⁵:

⁵Not all organizations use the same name convention for review formats, but these tend to be some of the most common.

Are the main and general objectives summarized?

Use the space below to list any missing references. Remember not to use this as an opportunity to gain citations of your own work.

Problem or Need Statement

This section should describe the general problem or need to be addressed by the project.

Does the proposal present the problem or need statement and how the project is relevant for a possible solution?

Are the problem or need statement related to the funding program's main objectives and scope?

Objectives

This section should describe the anticipated outcomes of the proposed project with respect to the problem or need.

Are the main and specific objectives of the project related to the funding program's own objectives?

Are the expected outcomes of the project connected with the problem or need statement of the proposal?

Methodologies

This section should detail the activities to be undertaken, describing exactly what steps are planned to take to reach the objectives. Timetables could be presented here, how to obtain certain data (if the case) and the methods that will be used for the required analysis, citing previous studies or reasons why these methods will likely lead to developing a viable model.

Does the proposal present details on the methods and techniques that will be used over the course of the project?

Are the proposed techniques/analyses appropriate to best address the project's goals and objectives?

Does the proposal present a clear and feasible timeline with activities in coherence to reach the project's main and specific objectives?

Does the grant proposal expose the reasons why the selected methods will likely lead to developing a viable model? (If applicable)

Evaluation (when applicable)

If an *Evaluation* of accomplishment is required by the funding program, this section should answer the following question:

Do the applicants propose a method or indicators to evaluate the accomplishment of the proposed objectives?

Budget (when applicable)

The budget describes the costs necessary to carry out the activities described in the proposal. Applicants should make clear which of those costs are to be paid by the funding program and which costs may be covered by other sources.

Is the proposed budget related to the activities to be developed over the course of the project?

Is the proposed budget coherent and sufficient to accomplish the objectives of the project?

 **STEP 4: MAKE YOUR FEEDBACK
CLEAR, CONSTRUCTIVE, AND ACTIONABLE**

ACTION: *Read* through your above notes with your categorized major and minor issues and *identify* ways to suggest improvements that are clear, constructive, and actionable.

Use the space below to list the **major issues** identified in STEP 3 and, for each one, suggest clear, constructive, and actionable ways to address them.

Use the space below to list the **minor issues** identified in STEP 3 and, for each one, suggest clear, constructive, and actionable ways to address it.

STEP 5: PUT IT ALL TOGETHER INTO A COHERENT NARRATIVE

If you took notes up to this point, most of your work is done and it should be about copying, pasting, and reorganizing text to make up your final review.

ACTION: Using your notes from STEP 2 and the following prompts, first *write* a short summary paragraph to contextualize the work and prime the reader for the rest of the review. Then use your notes from STEPS 3 and 4 to *present* your concerns, explanations on why there are issues, and recommendations on how to address those issues

What are the main strengths of the grant application proposal?

What are the main weaknesses of the grant application proposal?

Use the space below to assemble your Summary paragraph pulling sentences from your notes in STEP 2 and your answers to the above questions.

Use the space below to assemble your **Evidence and Example** section, drawing from the list of major and minor concerns and the relative suggestions on how to address them from STEP 4.

Use the space below to write your **Other points** section (if applicable). Answering the following questions may guide you through writing this section.

What one thing from this work have you learned?

Any final positive remarks?

Would you recommend additional reviews for this project proposal?

Would you recommend this project proposal be granted by the funding program?

 STEP 6: CHECK YOUR REVIEW **AND SHARE IT**

ACTION: *Read* through your above review draft all at once to make sure the language is clear, the feedback is constructive and actionable, and correct any typos. Finally, we recommend that you revisit your notes from STEP 1 and the [Bias Reflection Guide](#) to make sure your review is as objective and unbiased as it can be. Now it is ready to be shared with the Program Staff!

REFERENCES

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